

PROFESSIONALLY-ORIENTED LEXICON OF WORLD ECONOMICS: SYSTEMATIZATION AND FUNCTIONING IN SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE

Yergesheva Nazira Turalbayevna 2-course Phd researcher at TSUOS
ergeshevanazira@gmail.com (+90)9555020

Abstract. The present study is devoted to the systematization of professionally oriented lexical units in the field of international economics within the framework of scientific and popular science discourse. The research identifies seven lexical groups: general vocabulary, academic vocabulary, specialized terminology, neologisms, conventionalized expressions, professional jargon, and abbreviations. The findings demonstrate lexical diversity, a high degree of terminological density, and challenges associated with complex grammatical structures. The study substantiates the significance of cognitive factors and emphasizes the necessity of a systematic approach to teaching professional vocabulary.

Keywords. professionally oriented lexicon; international economics; discourse analysis; terminology; foreign language teaching

Annotatsiya. Mazkur tadqiqot xalqaro iqtisodiyot sohasida ilmiy hamda ilmiy-ommabop diskurs doirasida qo'llaniladigan professional yo'naltirilgan leksik birliklarni tizimlashtirishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotda yettita leksik guruh ajratib ko'rsatiladi: umumiste'mol leksikasi, akademik leksika, maxsus terminologiya, neologizmlar, klishelashgan birliklar, professional jargon hamda qisqartmalar. Natijalar leksik xilma-xillik, yuqori terminologik zichlik, shuningdek, murakkab grammatik konstruksiyalar bilan bog'liq qiyinchiliklarni yoritadi. Ishda kognitiv omillarning ahamiyati asoslab berilib, professional leksikani o'qitishda tizimli yondashuv zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: xalqaro iqtisodiyot; professional yo'naltirilgan leksika; terminologiya; diskurs; chet tilini o'qitish

Аннотация. Настоящее исследование посвящено систематизации профессионально ориентированных лексических единиц, используемых в рамках научного и научно-популярного дискурса в области международной экономики. В работе выделяются семь основных лексических групп: общепотребительная лексика, академическая лексика, специальная терминология, неологизмы, клишированные единицы, профессиональный жаргон и сокращения. Полученные результаты демонстрируют высокий уровень лексического разнообразия, значительную терминологическую плотность, а также трудности, связанные со сложными грамматическими конструкциями. В исследовании обосновывается важная роль когнитивных факторов и подчеркивается необходимость системного подхода к обучению профессиональной лексике.

Ключевые слова: международная экономика; профессионально ориентированная лексика; терминология; дискурс; обучение иностранному языку

In order to systematize the types of professionally oriented lexis in the field of world economics, widely used in both scientific and popular-scientific discourse, seven groups are presented below with illustrative examples. These examples are drawn from the textbooks *English for Business Studies: A Course for Business Studies and Economics Students* (MacKenzie, 2002), *Vocabulary Development and Practice for Higher-Level Students* (Wellman, 1996), as well as an online source.

Within the framework of the banking system and finance, the following lexical groups can be identified:

1. **General vocabulary:** bookkeeping, accounting, stocks and shares, bonds, auditing, market experts, shareholders, funds, plastic cards, liquid;
2. **Academic vocabulary specific to banking and finance:** international transaction, securities traded on the stock market, cash equivalents, direct debit;
3. **Specialized terminology:** accounts payable, consolidation (the process of a company merging into another company), hedge funds, up-market health, fund-flow statement, the Dow Jones Index, currency swap, fiscal matters, gold and foreign exchange reserves, import restrictions, visible and invisible trade, free trade;
4. **Authorial neologisms:** double-entry bookkeeping, non-dollar-based assets (such as European and Japanese equities and bonds), the act of reducing budgeted expenditures;
5. **Economic clichés involving metaphors, concepts, and fixed expressions:** managing derivative risks, capital flow, free market, potential market, the dollar falls/rises, the bond market shot through the roof, crazy things with money, conquer inflation, to be propped up by the Exchequer;
6. **Professional jargon:** financial sand traps, a financial sinkhole, cash;
7. **Abbreviations:** ATM (Automated Teller Machine), IMF (International Monetary Fund), GNP (Gross National Product), COMECON (Council for Mutual Economic Assistance), SPC (State Property Committee).

These examples demonstrate that the language of international economics incorporates a wide range of lexico-grammatical means, including general vocabulary, specialized terminology, compound structures, abbreviations, and internationalisms. Consequently, the defining features of discourse in this field include a high density of terminology, the use of descriptive modifiers and evaluative language, professional jargon, internationalisms and derivatives, as well as abbreviations.

From a grammatical perspective, difficulties arise from the use of infinitive and gerund constructions, passive voice, impersonal sentences, determiners, and related structures. Furthermore, both written and spoken communication involve pragmatic challenges, such as false cognates (“false friends”), alignment with situational and cultural contexts, and the use of interactional patterns or strategies. For example, students frequently confuse the semantics of words such as *fraction* (a small part/amount, a chemical fraction, a mathematical fraction), *perspective*

(viewpoint, outlook), and *realization* (implementation, understanding, achievement).

Thus, the development of professional foreign-language communicative competence is aimed at fostering the ability to interact effectively with partners in a professional context. This requires the practice of interactive skills within the framework of speech acts in order to achieve communicative goals, such as promoting products in international markets or improving product quality through new technologies. This aspect will be examined in greater detail in subsequent sections of this chapter.

It has been established that the primary causes of the aforementioned difficulties lie in the specificity and complexity of academic language and the structural organization of discourse, as well as in differences between the linguistic systems of the interacting languages (L1 and L2). This necessitates a specialized approach to mastering professionally oriented language, grounded in prior linguistic experience and the principle of approximation. At the same time, the examples provided indicate the existence of formal and functional challenges in learning and using lexis in the field of international economics. However, in the learning process, the student becomes a “cognizant” individual (i.e., one who acquires and processes knowledge), and therefore the perceived complexity of linguistic material varies depending on the learner’s cognitive abilities, as well as on the methods of presentation and practice employed by the instructor.

In this regard, it is important to consider these dimensions, as they enable foreign language instructors to determine the quantitative scope of vocabulary, assess the complexity of linguistic material, and identify effective strategies for its acquisition. It should also be noted that specialized dictionaries of difficult words exist, such as the *Oxford Dictionary of Difficult Words*, which can be effectively used both in selecting professional vocabulary and in developing instructional materials aimed at overcoming learning difficulties and interference.

In conclusion, the formation of professionally oriented lexis should be carried out within the framework of interdisciplinary knowledge and learning strategies, aimed at mastering the language of students’ future specialization, while taking into account the identified features and challenges.

Reference

1. MacKenzie, I. (2002). *English for business studies: A course for business studies and economics students*. Cambridge University Press.
2. Wellman, G. (1996). *Vocabulary development and practice for higher-level students*. Pearson Education.
3. Crandall, M. A. (1995). The role of language in academic learning. In J. E. Alatis, C. A. Strahle, B. Gallenberger, & M. Ronkin (Eds.), *Linguistics and the education of language teachers* (pp. xxx–xxx). Georgetown University Press.
4. Master, P. (2006). *English grammar and technical writing*. United States Department of State.

5. Ball, A. F., Farrar, E., & Lee, C. D. (2019). Teaching academic language: Principles and practices. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 63(1), 66–70.